

Project Website

Deliverable 6.2

Deliverable description

Deliverable 6.2 presents the process, steps and tools utilised in the creation of IMPETUS website.

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Summary

This document corresponds to the deliverable D6.2, *Project Website*, the second deliverable assigned to the WP6, Dissemination & Communication, led by EUSEA, European Science Engagement Association.

It presents the rationale for the development of the website, which is part of IMPETUS Communication Strategy. The IMPETUS website will be a key tool to share the development and outcomes of the project and to connect with different audiences. It is tightly connected with all work packages performative actions. IMPETUS' strategy regarding Communication and Dissemination are described in Deliverable 6.1

Communicating effectively the results of a EU-funded project is a relevant component of its success. It contributes to enhancing the impact of EU funding while building a stronger sense of an European community.

1. Introduction

“No one can whistle a symphony. It takes a whole orchestra to play it.”

H.E. Luccock

A sound and dynamic website is key to reach the publics the project has defined as its target ones. On the other hand, it contributes to explain the societal relevance of Citizen Science as a strategy to address complex global challenges by making science more inclusive, open and democratic.

The IMPETUS project was launched in September 2021. The website's main aim is to communicate the project's process, progress and its outcomes. IMPETUS core actions are linked to open calls for citizen science initiatives and for an European citizen science prize. Therefore, the website plays a key role in communicating clearly the various steps for these milestones and it is linked to all work packages due to its crosscutting role.

Its design responds to a continuous conversation with the partners, in order to fulfil the needs of the whole consortium.

2. Acronyms

EU	European Union
CS	Citizen Science
CSI	Citizen Science Initiatives
GD	Green Deal
UN SDG	United Nations Sustainable Development Goals
EUSEA	European Science Engagement Association

3. Overview of the project and objectives

IMPETUS will support and give recognition to Citizen Science (CS) by enabling a wider range of Citizen Science Initiatives (CSIs) to access innovative funding. It aims to bring CS closer to society and policymakers and to acknowledge its role in tackling the greatest challenges of our times. It will have a strong focus on enhancing its contributions to the Green Deal and the UN SDGs.

IMPETUS' four main objectives are:

- (O1) Opening routes to funding for a more diverse range of CSIs.
- (O2) Strengthening the bond between society and science.
- (O3) Recognising the role of CS in Europe.
- (O4) Enhancing the contribution of CS to achieving SDG and GD targets.

The support for Citizen Science Initiatives will be achieved through:

1. Three Open Calls, selecting the initiatives based on expected impacts, volunteer engagement, EDI, openness and quality data. 20k to kick-start 100 CSIs and 10k to sustain 25 CSIs will be offered addressing the pressing needs of European societies.
2. Setting up an accelerator that will provide an integrated programme of support, training, mentoring, and resources. The accelerator will facilitate peer learning, enable CSIs to contribute to UN SDG and GD targets and forge connections with [quadruple helix](#) stakeholders.
3. Launching the EU Prize for Citizen Science, awarded to CSIs for outstanding achievements, allowing them to continue and expand their work and showcase it to a broader audience. There will be one Grand Prize and two category awards (Diversity & Collaboration Award, Digital

Communities Award) during 3 years. The prize winners will be selected by an independent jury, one of whose members will be nominated by the citizen panel.

4. Convening a citizen panel that provides feedback on IMPETUS work.
5. Shaping EU policy in and with CS, through horizon scanning, anticipatory policy and action research, informing policy briefs, webinars and workshops with key policy stakeholders. The aim is to foster more CS data to inform evidence-based policies and identify future directions in CS policy.
6. Developing impact assessment tools and assessing the impact of CSIs and our own framework, especially on GD and SDG targets. Insights will be presented within the wider CS ecosystem and feed into recommendations for national and EU policies.

4. Project website

www.impetus4cs.eu

The IMPETUS website has been developed with the aim of presenting to the public the main activities of the project and showcasing its results. In addition, the website will be the core space for the dissemination of engagement opportunities such as the Open Calls, Accelerator and the Prize. EUSEA is the lead partner for managing the website content. The website has been built with the support of a web development company under the guiding principles of simplicity, accessibility, user-friendliness, and minimalism. The company appointed to develop an appealing website is the experienced Italian company [Web42](http://www.web42.it). They will be in charge of hosting along the project's timeline as well and one year after the project ends.

The website was developed in Wordpress, and it provides EUSEA with the possibility to update contents without advanced programming skills. It is user-friendly, and it features a clean, elegant and impactful front-end. The domain name of the website is www.impetus4cs.eu. Web42 based their web design taking into account the IMPETUS visual Identity, which is described in Deliverable 6.1.

The development of the website included online meetings for consultation with the partners at the initial stage, and then with the developers regular follow-ups via email. Communication between EUSEA and each partner was crucial, in order to gather information to be featured in the website.. The development of the website has been, in fact, a cooperative work. The whole Consortium has been involved in the process, and regular updates on progress have taken place during IMPETUS bi-weekly internal meetings. Several concepts were considered in the final proposed design:

- The IMPETUS website has to convey the spirit of the project, resonating with the core values of CS.

- The IMPETUS website must look appealing to the potential applicants coming from CSIs.
- The IMPETUS website must be easy to navigate, not overloaded with information.

4.1 Website navigation map

Building on several exchanges with the whole Consortium, the following wireframe was considered for the website. It is a menu bar that will be expanded as the project progresses. It was decided that there won't be any "Coming soon" page. Therefore, at this initial stage it has the following components:

4.1.1 Home page:

It contains pictures displayed in big format and running numbers showing IMPETUS' numbers.

It also shows the news, Twitter feed and the Consortium partners

4.1.2 About:

It presents a) the participating institutions, the team and its members, b) the way the project is structured in Work Packages and its connections with global frameworks such as the GD and the UN SDG and c) the operational

definition of CS. This definition is currently under discussion internally, it may change on the website without previous notice.

IMPETUS will support and give recognition to citizen science (CS) by enabling a wider range of citizen science initiatives (CSIs) to access innovative funding. We aim to bring CS closer to society and policymakers and to acknowledge its role in tackling the greatest challenges of our times. We will have a strong focus on enhancing its contributions to the Green Deal and the UN SDGs.

What is the Green Deal? The European Green Deal is a set of [policy initiatives](#) developed by the [European Commission](#) with the overarching aim of making the [European Union \(EU\)](#) climate neutral in 2050. It was approved in 2020. [Learn more here](#) and download the EU Green Deal [here](#).

We will support Citizen Science Initiatives through:

1. 3 Open Calls, selecting the initiatives based on expected impacts, volunteer engagement, EDI, openness and quality data. We will offer 20k to kick-start 100 CSIs and 10k to sustain 25 CSIs addressing the pressing needs of European society
2. Setting up an **accelerator** that will provide an integrated programme of support, training, mentoring, and resources. The accelerator will facilitate peer learning, enable CSIs to contribute to UN SDG and GD targets and forge connections with [quadruple helix](#) stakeholders.
3. Launching the **EU Prize for Citizen Science**, awarded to CSIs for outstanding achievements, allowing them to continue and expand their work and share their

4.1.3 EU Prize:

This section intends to inform all potential applicants about the EU Prize for CS. It will be expanded once the final setup for the Prize is finished according to the feedback of the PO on Deliverables 3.1 (Prize Working document) and 3.2 (Online submission tool).

4.1.4 Contact us:

A simple and straightforward form to fill in.

4.1.5 Social media links

The website shows and links the viewer to IMPETUS social media accounts:

Twitter: www.twitter.com/impetus4cs

LinkedIn: www.linkedin.com/company/impetus4cs

YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCMsXPTVGqvi8k_XaidHGyHA

5. Final remarks

The IMPETUS website is dynamic, allowing easy navigation by scrolling. The user will immediately grasp the available contents by scrolling down.

The website is a living tool, so it considers the creation of new pages for the coming needs. Among the new pages, it will have a media centre when the project starts gaining traction through the Open Calls and Awards.